

CHARACTERIZATION OF WOVEN COMPOSITES IN SHEAR DEFORMATION TILL WRINKLING

T.X. Yu¹, B. Zhu¹, and X.M. Tao²

¹ *Department of Mechanical Engineering, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology,
Clear Water Bay, Kowloon, Hong Kong*

² *Institute of Textiles and Clothing, Hong Kong Polytechnic University,
Hung Hom, Kowloon, Hong Kong*

SUMMARY: This paper presents a comprehensive experimental study on shear deformation, which is the primary deformation mode during stamping operations, for woven fabric composite sheets. In order to characterize in-plane large shear behavior of continuous fiber-reinforced textile composites, modified picture frame tests were conducted up to wrinkling under various temperatures and loading speeds. The effect of test conditions on shear modulus was investigated, and the geometric data obtained on test samples were then analyzed. Besides the direct observation, the onset of wrinkling in the composite sheets was also determined by identifying a densification point on the experimental curve and by a laser scanning technique on the test samples. Finally, the cross-sectional profiles of fabric samples during different stages of shear deformation were traced, helping to build up a theoretical model of the composite sheets during their large shear deformation.

KEYWORDS: wrinkling, densification, picture frame test, locking angle, woven fabric.

INTRODUCTION

Compared with metals and laminated composites, textile composites have many advantages due to their high specific stiffness, high strength, low weight and nice integral performance. By comparison, textile composites have no such limitation of interlaminar performance as laminated composites have. Most important is that, textile composites possess a high capacity to conform to complicated contours; thus, they are particularly suitable for manufacturing components with complex shape. Meanwhile, significant reductions of manufacturing costs in real industry can be achieved through highly efficient stamping operations.

However, formability of textile composite sheets, restricted by failure mechanisms such as wrinkling [1], remains as a crucial and challenging issue for stamping operations. Experiments have confirmed that wrinkling of the woven fabric will occur when the critical shear angle, named the “locking angle”, between the warp and weft yarns is reached. These wrinkles, caused by deforming the reinforcement beyond its locking angle, have the potential to induce numerous processing and potential strength problems [2]. Also, the wrinkles significantly affect the appearance of the final products. How to determine the locking angle, then to predict and prevent wrinkling during the forming process has become a focus of the studies in the field of textile composite forming.

PREVIOUS EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH

The “picture frame” test, as shown in Fig. 1, is one of the fundamental methods to characterize the in-plane shear behavior of textile composites. A square textile fabric is clamped into a fixture with four arms connected by four hinges. Since the arms can rotate freely at the hinges, the angle between two groups of yarns varies, thus resulting in a pure shear deformation of the fabric under an external diagonal tensile load.

Fig. 1: Set-ups of picture frame test

To normalize test data from different picture frame set-ups, Peng [3] proposed a general formula through an energy approach. Lussier and Chen [4] conducted a series of pure shear characterization experiments on plain woven composite. They analyzed the detailed stages that may occur during the large shear deformation, and made the corresponding physical explanations. The influence of temperature on shear behavior was also studied, which concluded that the stiffness of the material decreases with the increase of temperature. The tensile and shear properties were likewise studied by Lussier [5] and Boisse [6]. The locking angle when wrinkling occurs has been experimentally measured and analytically modeled by several researchers [7-9]. In their pin-joint model, assuming that the yarn width remains unchanged during shear deformation and wrinkling happens as soon as the gaps vanish, the locking angle, γ_c , is predicted as follows:

$$90^\circ - \gamma_c = \arcsin \frac{w}{w + \Delta} \quad (1)$$

where w is the yarn width and Δ is the initial gap between yarns.

However, traditional set-up has such a drawback that at large shear deformation, the joints of fixture would laterally compress the test sample, which accelerates the onset of wrinkling. To avoid this undesired interference, a modified fixture is adopted. Furthermore, It has been shown that the pin-joint model does not truly represent the shear behavior of woven fabrics. The lateral compression to yarns under shear deformation affects the initiation and evolution of wrinkles. This factor should be incorporated into the models so as to establish a more precise wrinkling criterion. In particular, the lateral yarn compression as well as the gap vanishing will be investigated in the present paper.

MODIFIED PICTURE FRAME TEST

Balanced plain-weave textile composite is fabricated from continuous E-glass fibers as the reinforcement and thermoplastic polypropylene (PP) as the matrix. The volume fraction of glass fiber is about 0.7. The fabric is made of two groups of yarns initially orthogonal to each

other. The glass and PP fibers are commingled together in the yarn at room temperature; while PP fibers begin to melt at about 160°C and soak into glass fibers to become matrix. The average geometric parameters of the specimen are shown in Table 1. To minimize the marginal restriction and facilitate the clamping of fabric, moderate corner cut-off on the square sample was still made, and yarns not clamped into the fixture were removed.

Table 1: Geometry of fabric and specimen

Property	Fabric	Specimen Size	
		Large	Small
Width of yarn (mm)	4.20		
Gap between yarns (mm)	0.98		
Thickness (mm)	1.60		
Off-angle		0°	0°
Yarn number		27×27	17×17
Side length (mm)		140×140	88×88

A modified fixture was designed to implement in-plane shear test as shown in Fig. 2. Most remains the same as before except the two middle joints, which deviate from the plane where the fabric is clamped, so that there will be no contact and no pressure imposed on to the fabric sample at its large shear deformation.

Fig. 2: Modified fixture of picture frame test: (a) front view; (b) side view

Figures 3 and 4 represent the results of the picture frame tests under different conditions. The shear response of the material is obviously non-linear, especially at large shear stage. On the other hand, the shear stiffness increases with loading speed while decreases with the increase of the temperature, especially beyond 180°C, due to the melting of PP fibers, which enlarges the gap between yarns and softens the material.

Fig. 3: Test results at 20°C under different loading speeds

Fig. 4: Test results under 10mm/min at elevated temperatures

However, at large deformation, the shear angle of the fabric does not follow that of the fixture. Instead, it gradually levels and will no longer increase after wrinkling. Further shear of the fixture only increases the wrinkling on the fabric sample. To correlate the variation of shear angle with the wrinkling phenomenon, shear angle of the fixture is compared with the measured one on the fabric. As denoted by Fig. 5, during small deformation, the shear angle of the fabric almost remains the same as that of the fixture. The maximum deviation in this stage is about 9.3%, which is caused by the errors in clamping and measurement. When the shear angle reaches about 57° , the increasing rate of that measured on fabric decreases compared with that of the fixture. Therefore, it may be estimated that wrinkling occurs between 55° and 60° in the shear angle of fabric. Another conclusion can be drawn from Fig. 5; that is, the test samples of different sizes have almost identical shear angles at the onset of wrinkling, which indicates that the size effect is unobvious.

Fig. 5: Measured shear angles of fixture and fabric

ANALYSIS OF LARGE SHEAR DEFORMATION

Three stages during large shear deformation

At room temperature, measurement was taken to find the relationship between the gap width and shear angle. It shows that when shear angle $\gamma < 50^\circ$, the reduction in the yarn width remains slight. In this stage, the lateral pressure to the yarns is small and there are still gaps between them (see Fig. 6). When the shear angle reaches about 50° , the yarn width decreases more quickly, which stands for the vanishing of gaps and a much larger lateral pressure to the yarn (see Fig. 7). Further shear results in local wrinkling on the fabric whilst the yarn width keeps as constant.

Fig. 6: Photo taken at $\gamma = 32^\circ$

Fig. 7: Photo taken at $\gamma = 50^\circ$

Based on the results, three typical stages can be identified during the large shear deformation of the woven composite sheets:

- 1) Stage I ($0 < \gamma < 50^\circ$): Two groups of yarns rotate with gaps.
- 2) Stage II ($50^\circ < \gamma < 60^\circ$): Yarns rotate without gaps under larger lateral pressure.
- 3) Stage III ($\gamma \approx 60^\circ$): Wrinkling due to the exhaustion of the yarns' compressibility.

Onset of wrinkling

In order to directly observe the wrinkling, the surface profile of the sample during the picture frame test was measured using Reversa Laser Scanner, as seen in Fig. 8. At a certain shear angle, the joints of fixture were tightened by screws, so that the shear deformation on the fabric could be “frozen”. After the scanner went through a 2-D horizontal region, the height values on the surface points of the sample were measured and recorded, thus a 3-D view of the sample surface could be displayed. The scanning region was $50 \times 50 \text{mm}^2$; the step length was 0.1mm; and the accuracy of measured height was $\pm 0.02 \text{mm}$.

Fig. 8: Laser scanning technique: (a) equipment; (b) scanning

Figure 9 shows the variation of surface profile of the specimen from the horizontal direction. It is seen distinctly that wrinkling occurs when the shear angle reaches about 58° , which agrees well with the result observed from Fig. 5.

Fig. 9: Surface profile at different shear angles: (a) $\gamma=56^\circ$; (b) $\gamma=58^\circ$; (c) $\gamma=59^\circ$

The second method to determine the exact onset of wrinkling is to find a densification point from the experimental load vs. displacement curve. Similar to the densification phenomenon of cellular materials under compression, wrinkling of a woven fabric can be regarded as the result of an in-plane densification, i.e., a generalized densification, since both processes involve a sudden increase of the material stiffness. Based on this analogy, the onset of wrinkling could be determined from an energy point of view by using the following formula:

$$\frac{df(s)}{ds} = \frac{d\left(\frac{\int_0^s F ds}{F}\right)}{ds} = 0 \Rightarrow s_c \quad (2)$$

where F and s are the diagonal tensile force and the corresponding displacement, respectively.

Determined by Eqn. (2), s_c is the critical displacement, at which wrinkling occurs. The integration can be done numerically based on the experimental F vs. s data. As a matter of fact, two extremums for the function $f(s)$ would exist for the whole test. However, the first extremum is relevant to the gap-vanishing phenomenon, which also results in a sudden increase of the shear stiffness, while the second one appears at the locking angle. To determine the second one, when the displacement reached the first extremum, the corresponding force and displacement are purposely re-set as zero. This will eliminate the gap-vanishing effect and re-focus on the wrinkling behavior in the later stage. Results indicate that wrinkling occurs at shear angle $\gamma \approx 57^\circ$ for large test sample under loading speed of 10mm/min; at $\gamma \approx 58^\circ$ for large sample under 500mm/min; and at $\gamma \approx 56.5^\circ$ for small sample under 10mm/min. This again concludes that loading speed and size effect do not significantly affect the onset of wrinkling.

Compared with previous literature that gave 36° for current test based on the simple formula Eqn. 1, the actual onset of wrinkling is much later in the picture frame test. This is because yarn width actually reduces during large shear deformation, which offers more space for the material to be sheared before wrinkling. In other words, the onset of wrinkling is greatly delayed as a result of the lateral compressibility of yarn.

Yarn cross-section during large shear deformation

Shear stiffness and wrinkling of the sample are closely related to the interaction between the two groups of yarns, such as the lateral compression to yarns and rotary friction at the joint regions. Hence, in order to build up a detailed model for large shear and to understand the mechanism of wrinkling, a key issue is to know the variation of yarn cross-section during the test. To observe the cross-section of yarns, first, before the shear test one group of yarns in the

fabric was dyed black to be different from the other. Then, the whole fabric was solidified, using epoxy curing agent, at different shear stages in the picture frame. Later, the sample was cut perpendicularly to the yarn direction. Finally, the cross-section of yarn was magnified as captured by a digital camera.

*Fig. 10: Cross-sections at different shear angles:
(a) $\gamma = 0^\circ$; (b) $\gamma = 20^\circ$; (c) $\gamma = 40^\circ$; (d) $\gamma = 60^\circ$; (e) wrinkling*

As shown in Fig. 10, the profile of cross-section remains an olive-shape during the whole shear deformation. The width reduces gradually under lateral compression, as mentioned before, with a little increase in the thickness. The nominal yarn thickness and cross-sectional area measured from the photos are plotted in Fig. 11. It is seen that when shear deformation is small, we observe a notable increase in the yarn thickness accompanied by a minor decrease in the cross-sectional area, which indicates a relatively small compression; at large shear deformation, the yarn thickness remains constant whilst the cross-sectional area is reduced much more, which stands for a large compression. Through the shear process, not only the gaps between yarns reduce, but the gaps inside a yarn also shrink. The interesting thing is that in the first stage, it is the outer gaps that mostly reduces; while in the second stage after vanish of the outer gap, the inner gap begins to shrink greatly. In this sense, two kinds of gaps dominate the two shear stages, respectively.

Fig. 11: Variation of yarn thickness and cross-sectional area

Moreover, Fig. 10 exhibits the change of the contact region between the upper and lower yarns, which affects the rotary friction at the joints of yarns and hence the shear stiffness of the sample. As revealed in Fig. 10(e), there is an angle between the lower boundaries of neighboring yarns. In other words, the yarn width reduction is restricted by wrinkling, i.e., after the width has been reduced to a certain limit, the fabric cannot be further deformed within the original plane, but buckles out of the plane. Analysis of these two different deformation modes will lay a basis for a theoretical model of textile composite sheets under large shear deformation up to wrinkling.

CONCLUSIONS

Winkling due to exceeding shear deformation acts as a predominate factor in the stamping operation of plain woven textile composites. The present study focuses on the experiment and

characterization of in-plane large shear deformation on the composite fabric. Experimental set-up, named “picture frame test”, was again employed but with new modifications, obtaining more accurate and reliable results. Geometrical parameters of the fabric during large shear deformation, as well as the onset of wrinkling, were determined. Differences between the pin-joint model used in previous papers and our observations are identified, with the causes being analyzed. Based on the observation of yarn cross-section, the mechanism of wrinkling behavior was further understood. As for further studies on the topic, a more precise theoretical model is now under construction based on the wrinkling mechanism described in the present paper.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Support from Hong Kong RGC grant HKUST6012/02E is gratefully acknowledged.

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